

1 **A Python code for detecting true Repeating Earthquakes from Self-**
2 **similar Waveforms (FINDRES)**

3 M. Sukan¹, S. Campanella², A. Vuan², N. Shakibay Senobari³

4
5 ¹National Institute of Oceanography and Applied Geophysics—OGS, Udine, Italy

6 ²National Institute of Oceanography and Applied Geophysics—OGS, Sgonico, Italy

7 ³University of California Riverside, Riverside, CA 92521-0144 (United States)

8
9 Corresponding author: Monica Sukan (msukan@ogs.it)

10 National Institute of Oceanography and Applied Geophysics – OGS, Italy

11
12
13
14 **Declaration of Competing Interests**

15 The authors acknowledge there are no conflicts of interest recorded.

16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23 **Cite this article as:**

24 Sukan, M., S. Campanella, A. Vuan, and N. Shakibay Senobari (2022). A Python Code for
25 Detecting True Repeating Earthquakes from Self-Similar Waveforms (FINDRES), *Seismol. Res.*
26 *Lett.* 93, 2847–2857, doi:10.1785/0220220048.

27

28 **Abstract**

29 Seismic data are generally scrutinized for repeating earthquakes to evaluate slip rates, changes in
30 the mechanical properties of a fault zone, and accelerating nucleation processes in foreshock and
31 aftershock sequences. They are also used to study velocity changes in the medium, earthquake
32 physics and prediction, and for constraining creep rate models at depth. For a robust detection of
33 repeaters, multiple constraints and different parameter configurations related to waveform similarity
34 have been proposed to measure cross-correlation values at a local seismic network and evaluate the
35 location of overlapping sources.

36 In this work, we developed a Python code to identify repeating earthquakes (FINDRES), inspired
37 by previous literature, which combines both seismic waveform similarity and differential S-P travel
38 time measured at each seismic station. A cross-spectral method is applied to evaluate precise
39 differential arrival travel times between earthquake pairs, allowing a sub-sample precision and
40 increasing the capacity to resolve an overlapping common source radius.

41 FINDRES is versatile and works with and without P and S-wave phase pickings, and has been
42 validated using synthetic and real data, providing reliable results. It would contribute to the
43 implementation of open-source Python packages in seismology, supporting the activities of
44 researchers and the reproducibility of scientific results.

45

46 **Introduction**

47 Repeating earthquakes (RE) are families of two or more events, usually of small magnitude, having
48 the same source rupture, location, and geometry, at different times. They represent recurring
49 seismic energy releases from the same single fault patch and are commonly found on creeping plate
50 boundaries, where asperities are loaded by aseismic slip (e.g., Nadeau and Johnson 1998; Igarashi
51 2010; Chen and Lapusta 2009). RE are observed in different tectonic settings involving strike-slip,
52 normal, and reverse faults (e.g., Duverger et al., 2018; Chen et al., 2008). They are helpful in

53 investigating and measuring temporal and spatial variations in fault creep rates (Chen et al., 2007;
54 Uchida and Bürgmann, 2019), slip directly on the fault independently of geodetic measurements,
55 and changes in the mechanical properties of a fault zone (Chaves et al., 2020). They have also been
56 observed during water injection experiments, providing images of the geometry and kinematics of
57 transient slip patches (Bourouis and Bernard 2007).

58 Many studies identify RE using waveform correlation or coherence (e.g., Igarashi et al., 2003;
59 Nadeau and McEvilly 1999; Schaff and Waldhauser 2005; Lengliné and Marsan 2009; Uchida and
60 Bürgmann 2019). When using the cross-correlation approach, the frequency band and the length of
61 the time window used in the calculation strongly impact the identification of the candidate repeaters
62 (Gao and Kao 2020). Long-time windows and broad frequency bands, together with the highest
63 cross-correlation values, help to ensure that the identified events truly overlap, but at the same time,
64 too-strict criteria may miss RE, despite the identical slip patch (e.g., Lengliné and Marsan 2009;
65 Gao et al., 2021). On the contrary, when insufficiently strict criteria are used, the associated events
66 could be nearby triggered earthquakes rather than true repeaters (Uchida 2019).

67 For this reason, robust RE detection by using multiple constraints and different parameter
68 configurations related to waveform similarity and physics-based methods have been proposed (i.e.,
69 Chen et al., 2008; Lengliné and Marsan 2009; Ellsworth and Bulut 2018; Shakibay Senobari and
70 Funning 2019; Gao et al., 2021). Using different approaches, such methods require waveform
71 similarity and at least 50% seismic source overlap to confirm a RE (Waldhauser and Ellsworth
72 2002).

73 To identify RE, we follow the approach proposed in Chen et al., (2008), and Shakibay Senobari and
74 Funning (2019). The method is based on the evidence that if two events have the same source
75 mechanism and their location overlaps, the seismic waveform at each station should be very similar,
76 as the difference between the S- and P- travel time arrivals ($\Delta S-P$). Using $\Delta S-P$ has the advantage of
77 preventing problems with station timing biases or uncertainties in the events' origin time (Chen et
78 al., 2008).

79 In particular, we developed an open-source Python code named FINDRES (Python Code for
80 Detecting true Repeating Earthquakes from Self-similar Waveforms), including Numpy (Harris et
81 al., 2020), Scipy (Virtanen et al., 2020), ObsPy (Beyreuther et al., 2010; Krischer et al., 2015),
82 Multitaper (Prieto 2022), and Matplotlib (Hunter 2007) dependencies. The efficiency of ObsPy has
83 been widely demonstrated in different open access packages for matched-filter detection methods
84 (Vuan et al., 2018; Chamberlain et al., 2018) and repeating earthquakes detection (e.g., Hotovec-
85 Ellis and Jeffries, 2016), among others.

86 In the next section, we provide a detailed description of the code workflow and describe the
87 architecture of the input data. FINDRES is open-source and available through a public GitHub
88 repository, where usage and additional information are provided.

89 The code is validated using both synthetic and real datasets. For evaluating FINDRES accuracy and
90 testing, we calculate synthetics by wavenumber integration and use some real data RE in the
91 Northern San Francisco Bay (California) provided by Shakibay Senobari and Funning (2019).

92

93 **Material and methods**

94 Figure 1 illustrates the FINDRES flow chart. An initial catalog of candidate repeating earthquakes
95 (CRE) is needed as a starting point to search for possible RE, together with the associated seismic
96 waveforms acquired by a pool of seismic stations. An inventory file of the seismic stations and a
97 suitable 1D P-and S velocity model (V_p , V_s) for the area under investigation are also required.
98 Optionally, associated P and S picks provided in one supported format can be used.

99 In the simplest case, CRE can be defined by analyzing earthquake inter-event distances using a
100 high-quality catalogue and selecting as CRE the events close enough in space, where the term
101 ‘enough’ depends basically on the station configuration and the quality of the starting catalog
102 available. More complete and sophisticated criteria can be adopted to define CRE, such as the ones
103 based on cross-correlation analysis (e.g., template matching), the output of waveform coherency,
104 etc. Whatever method is applied, the CRE catalog should be converted to a specific format. The

105 code uses a modified version of the ZMAP format (Wiemer, 2001), where the 11th and 12th columns
106 of the file are reserved for the event's name (its index in a parent catalog) and the path to the
107 waveform file. This indirection level provides a means to work with multiple catalogs and arbitrary
108 filenames. After CRE identification, the associated seismic waveform and station metadata should
109 be collected. Seismic data preparation consists of trimming CRE waveforms from continuous
110 streams by using P and S-wave theoretical travel times through a suitable 1D velocity model or
111 associated picks. The waveforms are cut to include a pre- and post-event time window; during later
112 analyses, select shorter chunks of data centered around the P or S picks are used.

113 After input data preparation, the code explores every CRE pair, using cross-correlation values and
114 differential arrival times of P and S waves. The code uses an early stopping strategy, and if the
115 cross-correlation criteria fail, it will skip the subsequent test. Waveforms pairs that pass both tests
116 are kept valid, and if we count enough stations, we consider them repeaters. We define a family of
117 RE as a connected component of the graph where the nodes are events, and two nodes are
118 connected if they are found to be a repeater doublet. In the end, FINDRES outputs the lists of
119 events found together, optionally with the files needed for relocalization and graphics. Since the
120 algorithm iterates over each possible event pair, its time complexity is quadratic depending on the
121 size of the starting catalog. Nonetheless, if one can divide the latter into separate clusters, then these
122 can be processed independently. Therefore, in the case of large-scale analyses, the recommendation
123 is to unpack the catalog of CRE into smaller ones (for example, exploiting candidates' location or
124 preliminary cross-correlation analyses) and leveraging the input system of FINDRES to process
125 them in parallel.

126 Numerical parameters for the cross-correlation and cross-spectrum analysis, together with the
127 definition of thresholds to be used for RE identification, should be set in a YAML *parameters*
128 configuration file, while the paths of the catalog and of the other input files are passed to the
129 program via a command-line interface. An example of the numerical *parameters* file is provided for
130 documentation purposes and is extensively commented on. The choice to use the popular YAML

131 data-serialization format for both input and output was made, given its readability and
132 comprehensive support.

133

134 *Cross-correlation values*

135 The cross-correlation (CC) values for each CRE pair at the available seismic stations are first
136 evaluated for an appropriate time window, including a pre-event interval before P-phase and an
137 interval after the S-phase. This choice allows considering both P and S-phases for stations at
138 different epicentral distances without fixing a priori the time window length. For each station, P-
139 and S-phases can be obtained by reading picks from a bulletin in standard formats or calculating the
140 theoretical travel time arrivals by a suitable earth model when P and S picks are not available (e.g.,
141 Li et al., 2020). As for the first solution, we implemented the readings for Hypoellipse (Lahr 1999),
142 Hypoinverse (Klein, 2002), NonlinLoc (Lomax et al., 2000), and QuakeML format, while
143 theoretical travel time calculations are made using the Java TauP Toolkit routines (Crotwell et al.,
144 1999). We also include the possibility to use an ObsPy picker to identify P arrival times, instead of
145 the theoretical values.

146 When reading phase picks from a detected event in a bulletin, S phases are often missing since S
147 arrival travel times can be difficult to recognize and mark. To overcome this difficulty, since we
148 want to consider arrival travel times for both P and S phases, we proceeded as follows: when there
149 is only a P-pick in the bulletin, the S-pick is approximately determined by supposing that S-wave
150 arrivals precede the maximum of the signal envelope after the P-pick. As a further constraint, we
151 force the maximum envelope to be found in a specific time window, centered using the P- and S-
152 arrival time criteria ($t_s - t_p$), taking into account the epicentral distance D and average crustal P and S
153 wave velocities (V_p and V_s).

154 After the P and S arrival travel time definition, the trimmed CRE waveforms are finally cross-
155 correlated in the time domain, using an appropriate frequency band, as suggested by Uchida 2019.

156 The user can implement the code, including different options for the correlation method (e.g. Gao

157 and Kao, 2020) or other features.

158 The frequency bandwidth is usually fixed based on the source dimension (r) and corner frequency
159 (f_c). For recognizing overlapping events with approximately the same source size, we must account
160 for frequencies (f) $f \geq V_s/4r$, where r is the source radius. When a circular source radius is
161 assumed, r can be estimated using the following equation (e.g., Eshelby 1957):

$$162 \quad r = ((7/16)(M_0/\Delta\sigma))^{1/3} \quad (1)$$

163 where M_0 is the seismic moment, and $\Delta\sigma$ is the uniform stress drop. While M_0 is generally well
164 estimated, $\Delta\sigma$ can be poorly constrained. Its incorrect assumption can erroneously estimate the
165 seismic source radius and classify close events as repeaters and vice versa. The upper bound of the
166 bandwidth should instead be lower than the corner frequency to reduce the possibility of excluding
167 events with different rupture patterns (i.e., slip directivity) but overlapping source areas compatible
168 with RE (Uchida, 2019). The corner frequency increases as the magnitude and seismic source
169 radius decrease. In general, even the detectable distance, which corresponds to the critical distance
170 beyond which the event of a given magnitude can be detected, decreases with magnitude (e.g., Li et
171 al., 2020). Commonly, the corner frequency is computed using spectral ratios (Andrews 1986) or
172 empirical Green's functions (Hough and Dreger 1995) or simplified relationships using dynamic
173 rupture models (e.g., Brune 1970; Madariaga 1976).

174 Since the CRE catalog can have widespread magnitude ranges (corresponding to different source
175 radii and corner frequencies), we consider defining different bandpass filters, specified using the
176 input parameter file. The first step of the analysis performs the CC, and when a threshold cross-
177 correlation value is reached (e.g., 0.7-1.0), the procedure calculates the ΔS -P by applying the cross-
178 spectrum methods at each seismic station.

179

180 *Cross-spectrum for ΔS -P estimation*

181 To measure precise differential ΔS -P arrival times between CRE pairs, we apply the cross-spectral
182 method by following the approach described in Poupinet et al. (1984) and using the ObsPy port

183 (Krischer et al., 2015). The spectral method is preferred since it allows sub-sample precision to
184 resolve minimal source separation.

185 Data processing at a single station requires a pre-alignment of the waveforms for each pair of events
186 based on the relative shift for which a maximum cross-correlation value is obtained. This step is
187 essential, and signal padding is also required to have the same number of samples for the signals
188 under process.

189 To compute the cross-spectrum, we selected two different time intervals around P-phase and S-
190 phase arrival travel times for each station and used the Multitaper module developed in Python
191 (Prieto 2022). Cross-spectrum parameters are set in the parameter file. As described in the previous
192 section, P and S window lengths are tailored based on P and S travel times.

193 The delay times for both P- and S-waves are calculated by the best-fitting slope of the phase
194 spectrum for points with coherence above a specific value. The value can be tailored based on the
195 case study but should be high enough to guarantee high coherence in a specific frequency band
196 (e.g., 0.85 or above).

197 To constrain further, we can extend the frequency range beyond the maximum frequency used
198 during the cross-correlation and specify a minimum number of points above the coherence
199 threshold to evaluate fitting. Then, the relative difference between P and S delay times is taken to
200 estimate the $\Delta S-P$ time between the events.

201

202 *Similarity space domain*

203 The similarity space domain identifies earthquake pairs on the same asperity at different times.
204 After the cross-correlation and cross-spectrum analysis is performed, we need to define CC and
205 $\Delta S-P$ thresholds indicating RE that share at least 50% of the seismic source. Between these
206 thresholds, the similarity space domain took place, and the number of seismic stations inside it can
207 be evaluated for a proper RE identification (Chen et al., 2008).

208 While the CC threshold can be fixed by choosing a good value, the $\Delta S - P$ threshold varies
209 according to the seismic source radius. We provide a utility to explore various settings to get an
210 average value for the $\Delta S-P$ domain expected for an RE pair, based on magnitude ranges and the
211 adopted $\Delta\sigma$ and velocity model.

212 The selected CC and $\Delta S-P$ thresholds that define the similarity space domain must be specified in
213 the parameters file, together with the minimum number of seismic stations (N_s) required. Since the
214 source radius and N_s varies based on magnitude ranges, the code enables selecting $\Delta S-P$ thresholds
215 and N_s for different magnitude ranges. The selected N_s depends on the available stations and the
216 size of the events.

217 Sampling frequency, number of stations, magnitude range and hypocentral distance are related and
218 results strictly depend on the data quality. The code itself can be used with various configuration
219 parameters to perform some tests before approaching the problem. These tests can provide
220 indications on the setup of parameters.

221 The procedure loops for all CRE pairs and stores the resulting RE in a list. All RE families with two
222 or more events are grouped together when they share a common event in the final step. Different
223 parameter configurations can be used to perform stress tests and evaluate the stability of the
224 identified RE.

225 We can relocate RE families with multiple events by applying a double difference relocation
226 algorithm. For this reason, as a by-product, we also generate an input file to be used with HypoDD
227 code (Waldhauser and Ellsworth, 2000). To develop it, we follow the technique of Chen et al.
228 (2008), where the relative times for P and S (called t_{tp} and t_{ts} , respectively) are derived from the S-
229 P time (S_mP) and V_p/V_s ratio (e.g., Shakibay Senobari and Funning, 2019):

$$230 \quad t_{tp} = S_mP / ((V_p/V_s) - 1) \quad (2)$$

$$231 \quad t_{ts} = S_mP / (1 - (V_s/V_p)) \quad (3)$$

232 Using this approach, relocated events' absolute locations may not be remarkably accurate, but their
233 relative position is improved (Chen et al., 2008), and multiple REs can be classified.

234 When using HypoDD, we recommend using the singular value decomposition (SVD). It is the
235 standard method for solving the least-squares problem. Other choices include the conjugate
236 gradients method (LSQR, Paige and Saunders, 1982), which is used when SVD is not
237 computationally feasible and sacrifices accuracy for speed (Waldhauser and Ellsworth, 2000). The
238 number of RE in a family is usually less than 100, so SVD, which is suitable for a smaller number
239 of events, is appropriate.

240

241 **Application to synthetic and real data**

242 We apply FINDRES to a synthetic dataset to observe the CC and ΔS -P estimated on event pairs of
243 known seismic sources. Synthetic seismograms are generated using a frequency-wavenumber code
244 (Herrmann, 2013) and a simple 1D velocity model (Table 1).

245

Layer depth (km)	Vp (km/s)	Vp/Vs
0.00	4.10	1.84
2.00	5.10	1.77
7.86	5.79	1.79
17.80	6.34	1.73
42.00	8.00	1.78

246

247 Table 1 – Velocity model used to generate synthetic seismograms.

248

249 We investigate the CC values and the differences between the theoretical and calculated ΔS -P for
250 pairs of earthquakes with the same focal mechanism (strike, dip, rake 242°, 40°, 80° respectively),
251 depth (10 km), M_0 (2.24e11 Nm, corresponding to an M_w 1.5) and corner frequency (25 Hz),
252 assuming a stress drop of 1 MPa. We generate synthetic seismograms at epicentral distances of
253 about 15 km and the azimuth of about 226°, at a sampling rate of 100 Hz.

254 We simulate pairs of events characterized by inter-event distances (d) of 5, 10 m, 50 m, and 100 m.

255 The spaces between the events are defined based on the size of the seismic source to investigate

256 their overlap ($> 50\%$ for d of about 5 and 10 m, 50% for d of about 50 m, and $< 50\%$ for d of about
257 100 m). Assuming a stress drop of 1 MPa, the corresponding source radius using specified M_0 is
258 approximately 46 m, using formula (1).

259 FINDRES is applied to synthetic pairs. The experiment is used to validate the code and do not try
260 to mimic any real case or evaluate limits due to the network configuration related to magnitude-
261 distance couples. Figure 2 shows an example of earthquakes characterized by inter-event distance
262 (d) of about 10 m. CC is estimated using a 1-25 Hz bandpass filter, suitable to recognize possible
263 non-overlapping events and not exceeding the corner frequency.

264 While the cross-correlation threshold can be fixed by choosing a conservative value (e.g., 0.9), the
265 $\Delta S - P$ threshold varies according to the magnitude of the events, stress drop, and seismic radius.
266 For synthetics, using M_w 1.5, stress drop of about 1 MPa, the velocity model in Tab. 1, and event-
267 station distances of 15 km, the $\Delta S-P$ threshold defining the spatial similarity domain is estimated at
268 approximately 0.00575 s. This value is less than the single sample accuracy achievable using 100
269 Hz data. FINDRES results are shown in the similarity space domain in Figure 3a, where the
270 agreement between theoretical and calculated $\Delta S-P$ can be observed. We also investigate how noise
271 incorporated in the synthetic signal can modify the correlation and coherence-based S-P time,
272 adding different signal-to-noise ratio levels (SNR) of random noise to the synthetic data (SNR 2, 3,
273 and 5). SNR is calculated using the root-mean-square (rms), where signal and noise are defined by
274 the rms amplitude in a window 1 s after and 3 s before the P arrival time, respectively. We can
275 observe that both cross-correlation and $\Delta S-P$ lose accuracy, but still, the values are within the
276 selected similarity space domain (Figure 3b-d) up to SNR 2. The synthetic also shows a
277 demonstration of closely located but not overlapping events (green symbols in Figure 3). The green
278 symbols correspond to pair of earthquakes with high cross correlation values ($CC > 0.90$ in Figure
279 3a-d), located outside the similarity space domain (grey box), and therefore rejected by the
280 procedure. In this case it is evident that the evaluation of the delta S-P is essential to correctly
281 identify or discard RE.

282 To validate FINDRES using a real dataset, we applied the code to two RE families identified by
 283 Shakibay Senobari and Funning (2019) in the Northern San Francisco Bay Area (Table 2).
 284 For these events, we use waveform data, metadata, and picks from the Northern California
 285 Earthquake Data Center, NCEDC (2014).
 286

Id_RE	Id_NCEDC	Lat (deg)	Long (deg)	Date (yyyy-mm-dd)	Time (hh:mm:ss)	Mag
0	122842	-122.99767	38.88830	1988-08-25	21:48:30.40	1.87
	484038	-122.99550	38.88750	1996-11-08	07:52:19.60	2.15
	21442564	-122.99617	38.88733	2005-03-01	10:01:21.00	2.08
	72388871	-122.99117	38.88750	2015-01-30	06:48:41.18	2.04
1	128170	-122.76884	38.54000	1988-12-07	06:47:34.21	2.04
	21128020	-122.76817	38.54183	2000-10-02	00:12:38.37	1.91
	71439381	-122.77167	38.54550	2010-07-30	05:57:34.30	1.72

287
 288 Table 2 - Two RE families (Id_RE #0, #1) (from Shakibay Senobari and Funning, 2019).
 289 Associated values (latitude, longitude, date, time and magnitude) for each event are taken from
 290 NCEDC (2014).

291
 292 All the parameters and the data used for the test are described in the FINDRES GitHub repository,
 293 together with all the necessary information to reproduce the results. In particular, we used a 1-20 Hz
 294 bandpass filter to evaluate the CC values, while the delay times for P and S-waves are estimated
 295 using the cross-spectrum plot versus frequency. Delay times are obtained by fitting the slope of the
 296 points with coherence above 0.88 for a portion of a signal centered on P and S arrival travel times
 297 (Figure 4). The lower bound of the cross-correlation used for repeated earthquake detections in the
 298 time series is about (0.90). This is not a rule. When using phase coherence, we can choose to use a
 299 slightly lower value (0.88) to account for possible numerical instability and ripples at certain
 300 frequencies. In general, we recommend choosing a value greater than 0.85 and less than or equal to
 301 0.90.

302 For source radius estimation, we use 3MPa as stress drop, the Mw-Mo conversion, and the velocity
 303 model of Shakibay Senobari and Funning (2019). We established the similarity space domain using

304 0.9 for CC and 0.007 s for $\Delta S-P$, and set N_s 3 to declare a RE.
305 Using FINDRES and the HypoDD code, we obtained consistent results with the published ones
306 (Shakibay Senobari and Funning, 2019). Figure 5 shows the similarity space domain for the pairs
307 with Id #21128020 and #71439381 in Table 2, and Figure 6 the final HypoDD location for the
308 corresponding RE family (Id_RE #1).

309

310 **Conclusions**

311 We developed a code that helps identify true RE from self-similar waveforms. RE represent an
312 intriguing subject since they are able to provide insights on the fault strength and the interseismic
313 slip independently of geodetic observations. Moreover, small magnitude earthquakes repeated in
314 space and time could be associated with aseismic slip in foreshocks and aftershock sequences and
315 thus, indicative of variations in tectonic loading and possible creeping.

316 We describe here the FINDRES Python code implementation that combines seismic waveform
317 similarity by using cross-correlation and differential S-P travel times.

318 The code can be applied to different types of earthquakes. The data preparation and setup of input
319 parameters must be selected appropriately considering the magnitude ranges/corner frequencies and
320 network configurations. The seismometer characteristics and the sampling frequency limit the
321 frequency band available for analysis, i.e., we cannot investigate RE if the corner frequency is
322 higher than the Nyquist frequency. Uchida 2019 and Li et al. (2020), among others, show frequency
323 and magnitude ranges suitable for detecting repeated earthquakes.

324 The code itself can be used with various configuration parameters to perform some preliminary
325 tests. These tests can help in the setup of the input parameters and approaching the problem.

326 FINDRES is versatile and works with and without P and S-wave phase pickings. A suitable velocity
327 model for the area under investigation is required in the second case. The procedure is also
328 applicable to seismic catalogs built by non-standard waveform-based location methods, for which P
329 and S picks are not always available.

330 Finally, the code is validated using wavenumber integration synthetic seismograms, and a real case
331 study is reproduced to confirm a RE family in Northern California.

332

333 **Data and Resources**

334 Seismic waveform and picks phases can be accessed through the Northern California Earthquake
335 Data Center (NCEDC), doi:10.7932/NCEDC. In particular, we used the NCSN catalog and Phase in
336 Hypoinverse format, available at <https://ncedc.org/ncedc/catalog-search.html>, last accessed January
337 2022. Wavenumber integration seismograms are calculated using Computer Programs in
338 Seismology (Herrmann, 2013). FINDRES code and data used in this work are available at
339 <https://github.com/msugan/FINDRES>.

340

341

342 **Acknowledgments**

343 The authors would like to thank the Associate Editor, Calum J. Chamberlain, and one anonymous
344 reviewer for their constructive comments. Software implementation is partly supported by the
345 project “Real-time earthquake rIsk reduction for a reSilient Europe” (RISE), funded by the
346 European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under Grant Agreement Number
347 821115, and by Istituto Nazionale di Oceanografia e di Geofisica Sperimentale-OGS and Consorzio
348 INteruniversitario pEr il Calcolo Automatico dell’Italia Nord Orientale (CINECA) under High
349 Performance Computing - Training and Research for Earth Sciences (HPC-TRES) program award
350 number 2021-01. Nader Shakibay Senobari acknowledges support from U.S. Geological Survey
351 (USGS) Award G20AP00092 and National Science Foundation (NSF) Award ID 2103976. The
352 authors thank the Python and ObsPy communities for sharing open-source codes and ideas, which
353 can be used and implemented to enrich existing seismological codes.

354

355 **References**

- 356 Andrews, D.J. (1986). Objective Determination of Source Parameters and Similarity of
357 Earthquakes of Different Size, *Earthquake Source Mechanics*, American
358 Geophysical Union, Washington DC, 259-268.
359 <https://doi.org/10.1029/GM037p0259>
- 360 Beyreuther, M., R. Barsch, L. Krischer, T. Megies, Y. Behr, and J. Wassermann (2010). ObsPy: A
361 Python toolbox for seismology, *Seismol. Res. Lett.* **81**(3) 530–533.
362 <https://doi.org/10.1785/gssrl.81.3.530>
- 363 Bourouis, S., and P. Bernard (2007). Evidence for coupled seismic and aseismic fault slip during
364 water injection in the geothermal site of Soultz (France), and implications for
365 seismogenic transients, *Geophys. J. Int.* **169** 723–732.
366 <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-246X.2006.03325.x>
- 367 Brune, J.N. (1970). Tectonic stress and the spectra of seismic shear waves from earthquakes, *J.*
368 *Geophys. Res.* **75** 4997– 5009.
- 369 Chamberlain, C.J., C.J. Hopp, C.M. Boese, E. Warren-Smith, D. Chambers, S.X. Chu, K.
370 Michailos, and J. Townend (2018): EQcorrscan: Repeating and Near Repeating
371 Earthquake Detection and Analysis in Python, *Seismol. Res. Lett.* **89**(1) 173-181.
372 <https://doi.org/10.1785/0220170151>
- 373 Chaves, E.J., S.Y. Schwartz, and R.E. Abercrombie (2020). Repeating earthquakes record fault
374 weakening and healing in areas of megathrust postseismic slip, *Science Advances* **6**
375 (32) eaaz9317. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.aaz9317>
- 376 Chen, K.H., R.M. Nadeau, and R.-J. Rau (2008). Characteristic repeating microearthquakes on an
377 arc-continent collision boundary zone: the Chihshang fault of eastern Taiwan, *Earth*
378 *Planet. Sci. Lett.*, **276**(3-4) 262–272. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.epsl.2008.09.021>

- 379 Chen, K.H., R.M. Nadeau, and R.-J. Rau (2007). Towards a universal rule on the recurrence
380 interval scaling of repeating earthquakes? *Geophys. Res. Lett.* **34** L16308.
381 <https://doi.org/10.1029/2007GL030554>
- 382 Chen, T., and N. Lapusta (2009). Scaling of small repeating earthquakes explained by interaction
383 of seismic and aseismic slip in a rate and state fault model, *J. Geophys. Res.* **114**
384 B01311. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2008JB005749>
- 385 Crotwell, H.P., T.J. Owens, and J. Ritsema (1999). The TauP Toolkit: flexible seismic travel-
386 time and ray-path utilities, *Seismol. Res. Lett.*, **70**(2), 154–160.
387 <https://doi.org/10.1785/gssrl.70.2.154>
- 388 Duverger, C., S. Lambotte, P. Bernard, H. Lyon-Caen, A. Deschamps, and A. Nercessian
389 (2018). Dynamics of microseismicity and its relationship with the active
390 structures in the western Corinth Rift (Greece), *Geophys. J. Int.* **215** 196–221.
391 <https://doi.org/10.1093/gji/ggy264>
- 392 Ellsworth, W.L., and F. Bulut (2018). Nucleation of the 1999 Izmit earthquake by a triggered
393 cascade of foreshocks, *Nat. Geosci.* **11** 531–535. [https://doi.org/10.1038/s41561-](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41561-018-0145-1)
394 [018-0145-1](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41561-018-0145-1)
- 395 Eshelby, J.D. (1957). The determination of the elastic field of an ellipsoidal inclusion, and
396 related problems, *Proc. R. Soc. Lond. A*, 241 1226 (pg. 376-396).
- 397 Gao, D., and H. Kao, (2020). Optimization of the match-filtering method for robust repeating
398 earthquake detection: The multisegment cross-correlation approach, *Journal of*
399 *Geophysical Research:* **125**, e2020JB019714. [https://doi.org/](https://doi.org/10.1029/2020JB019714)
400 [10.1029/2020JB019714](https://doi.org/10.1029/2020JB019714)

401 Gao, D., H. Kao, and B. Wang (2021). Misconception of Waveform Similarity in the
402 Identification of Repeating Earthquakes, *Geophys. Res. Lett.* **48**(13),
403 e2021GL092815. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2021GL092815>

404 Harris, C.R., K.J. Millman, S.J. van der Walt, et al., (2020). Array programming with NumPy,
405 *Nature* **585**, 357–362 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-020-2649-2>

406 Herrmann, R.B. (2013). Computer Programs in Seismology: An Evolving Tool for Instruction
407 and Research, *Seismol. Res. Lett.* **84**(6) 1081–1088.
408 <https://doi.org/10.1785/0220110096>

409 Hotovec-Ellis, A.J., and C. Jeffries (2016). Near Real-time Detection, Clustering, and Analysis
410 of Repeating Earthquakes: Application to Mount St. Helens and Redoubt
411 Volcanoes – *Invited*, presented at Seismological Society of America Annual
412 Meeting, Reno, Nevada, 20 Apr.

413 Hough, S.E., and D.S. Dreger (1995). Source parameters of the 4/23/92 Joshua Tree, California,
414 earthquake and its aftershocks: empirical Green’s function analysis of TERRA
415 scope and GEOS data, *Bull. Seism. Soc. Am.* **85** 1576–1590.

416 Hunter, J. D. (2007). Matplotlib: A 2D Graphics Environment, *Computing in Science &*
417 *Engineering*, 9(3) 90-95.

418 Igarashi, T., T. Matsuzawa, and A. Hasegawa (2003). Repeating earthquakes and interplate
419 aseismic slip in the northeastern Japan subduction zone, *J. Geophys. Res.* **108** B5
420 2249. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2002JB001920>

421 Igarashi, T. (2010). Spatial changes of inter-plate coupling inferred from sequences of small
422 repeating earthquakes in Japan, *Geophys. Res. Lett.* **37** L20304.
423 <https://doi.org/10.1029/2010GL044609>

- 424 Klein, F.W. (2002). User's guide to HYPOINVERSE-2000: a Fortran program to solve for
425 earthquake locations and magnitudes, *U.S. Geol. Surv. Prof. Pap.* 2002, rep. 02-17
426 1–123.
- 427 Krischer, L., T. Megies, R. Barsch, M. Beyreuther, T. Lecocq, C. Caudron, and J. Wassermann
428 (2015). ObsPy: a bridge for seismology into the scientific Python ecosystem,
429 *Comput. Sci. Discov.* **8** 014003. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1749-4699/8/1/014003>
- 430 Lahr, J. C. (1999). HYPOELLIPSE: A computer program for determining local earthquake
431 hypocentral parameters, magnitude, and first-motion pattern (Y2K Compliant
432 Version). *Open-file Report 99-023, US Geological Survey, Golden, Colorado,*
433 *paper and on-line editions, 112 pp.*
- 434 Lengliné, O., and D. Marsan (2009). Inferring the coseismic and postseismic stress changes caused
435 by the 2004 Mw = 6 Parkfield earthquake from variations of recurrence times of
436 microearthquakes, *J. Geophys. Res.* **114** B10303.
437 <https://doi.org/10.1029/2008JB006118>
- 438 Li, L., J. Tan, B. Schwarz, F. Staněk, N. Poiata, P. Shi et al., (2020). Recent advances and
439 challenges of waveform-based seismic location methods at multiple scales. *Reviews*
440 *of Geophysics* **58** e2019RG000667. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2019RG000667>
- 441 Lomax, A., J. Virieux, P. Volant, and C. Berge-Thierry (2000). Probabilistic Earthquake Location
442 in 3D and Layered Models. In: Thurber C.H., Rabinowitz N. (eds) *Advances in*
443 *Seismic Event Location. Modern Approaches in Geophysics*, vol 18. Springer,
444 Dordrecht. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-015-9536-0_5
- 445 Madariaga, R. (1976). Dynamics of an expanding circular fault, *Bull. Seismol. Soc. Am.* **66** 639–
446 666.

447 Nadeau, R.M., and L.R. Johnson (1998). Seismological studies at Parkfield VI: moment release
448 rates and estimates of source parameters for small repeating earthquakes, *Bull.*
449 *Seismol. Soc. Am.* **88**(3) 790–814.

450 Nadeau, R.M., and T.V. McEvilly (1999). Fault slip rates at depth from recurrence intervals of
451 repeating microearthquakes, *Science* **285** 718–721.
452 <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.285.5428.718>

453 NCEDC (2014), Northern California Earthquake Data Center. UC Berkeley Seismological
454 Laboratory. Dataset. <https://doi.org/10.7932/NCEDC>

455 Paige C., and M. Saunders (1982). LSQR: An Algorithm for Sparse Linear Equations and Sparse
456 Least Squares, *ACM Transactions on Mathematical Software*, **8** 43–71.
457 <https://doi.org/10.1145/355984.355989>

458 Poupinet, G., W.L. Ellsworth, and J. Frechet (1984). Monitoring velocity variations in the crust
459 using earthquake doublets: an application to the Calaveras fault, California, *J.*
460 *Geophys. Res.* **89**(B7) 5719–5731.

461 Prieto, G.A. (2022). Multitaper: A multitaper spectrum analysis package in Python, *Seis. Res.*
462 *Lett.*, **93**(3) 1922–1929. <https://doi.org/10.1785/0220210332>

463 Schaff, D.P., and F. Waldhauser (2005). Waveform cross-correlation-based differential travel-time
464 measurements at the Northern California Seismic Network, *Bull. Seismol. Soc. Am.*
465 **95**(6) 2446–2461. <https://doi.org/10.1785/0120040221>

466 Shakibay Senobari, N., and G.J. Funning (2019). Widespread Fault Creep in the Northern San
467 Francisco Bay Area Revealed by Multistation Cluster Detection of Repeating
468 Earthquakes, *Geophys. Res. Lett.* **46** 6425–6434.
469 <https://doi.org/10.1029/2019GL082766>

- 470 Uchida, N., J. Nakajima, A. Hasegawa, and T. Matsuzawa (2009). What controls interplate
471 coupling? Evidence for abrupt change in coupling across a border between two
472 overlying plates in the NE Japan subduction zone, *Earth Planet. Sci. Lett.* **283** 111–
473 121. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.epsl.2009.04.003>
- 474 Uchida, N., and R. Bürgmann (2019). Repeating earthquakes, *Annual Review of Earth and*
475 *Planetary Sciences* **47** 305-332. [https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-earth-053018-](https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-earth-053018-060119)
476 [060119](https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-earth-053018-060119)
- 477 Uchida, N. (2019). Detection of repeating earthquakes and their application in characterizing slow
478 fault slip, *Prog. Earth Planet Sci.* **6** 40. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40645-019-0284-z>
- 479 Virtanen, P., R. Gommers, T.E. Oliphant, M. Haberland, T. Reddy, D. Cournapeau, E. Burovski,
480 P. Peterson, W. Weckesser, J. Bright, S.J. van der Walt, M. Brett, J. Wilson, K.J.
481 Millman, N. Mayorov, A.R.J. Nelson, E. Jones, R. Kern, E. Larson, CJ Carey, Í.
482 Polat, Y. Feng, E.W. Moore, J. VanderPlas, D. Laxalde, J. Perktold, R. Cimrman, I.
483 Henriksen, E.A. Quintero, C.R. Harris, A.M. Archibald, A.H. Ribeiro, F.
484 Pedregosa, P. van Mulbregt, and SciPy 1.0 Contributors. (2020) SciPy 1.0:
485 Fundamental Algorithms for Scientific Computing in Python. *Nature Methods*,
486 **17**(3), 261-272.
- 487 Vuan, A., M. Sagan, G. Amati, and A. Kato (2018). Improving the Detection of Low-Magnitude
488 Seismicity Preceding the Mw 6.3 L'Aquila Earthquake: Development of a Scalable
489 Code Based on the Cross-Correlation of Template Earthquakes, *Bull. Seismol. Soc.*
490 *Am.* **108**(1) 471-480. <https://doi.org/10.1785/0120170106>
- 491 Waldhauser, F., and W.L. Ellsworth (2000). A double-difference earthquake location algorithm:
492 Method and application to the northern Hayward fault, California, *Bull. Seismol.*
493 *Soc. Am.* **90**(6) 1353–1368.

494 Waldhauser, F., and W. L. Ellsworth (2002), Fault structure and mechanics of the Hayward Fault,
495 California, from double-difference earthquake locations, *J. Geophys. Res.*,107(B3),
496 2054. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2000JB000084>

497 Wiemer, S. (2001). A software package to analyze seismicity: ZMAP, *Seismol. Res. Lett.* **72**(3)
498 373-382. <https://doi.org/10.1785/gssrl.72.3.373>

499

500

501

502

503

504

505

506

507

508

509

510

511

512

513

514

515

516

517

518

Accepted

519

520 **Full mailing address for each author**

521 **Sugan Monica** (*corresponding author*)

522 Centro di Ricerche Sismologiche

523 Istituto Nazionale di Oceanografia e di Geofisica Sperimentale - OGS

524 via Treviso 55, Udine – Italia

525 msugan@ogs.it

526

527 **Campanella Stefano**

528 Centro di Ricerche Sismologiche

529 Istituto Nazionale di Oceanografia e di Geofisica Sperimentale - OGS

530 Borgo Grotta Gigante n. 42/c, 34010 Sgonico (Trieste) - Italia

531 scampanella@ogs.it

532

533 **Vuan Alessandro**

534 Centro di Ricerche Sismologiche

535 Istituto Nazionale di Oceanografia e di Geofisica Sperimentale - OGS

536 Borgo Grotta Gigante n. 42/c, 34010 Sgonico (Trieste) - Italia

537 avuan@ogs.it

538

539 **Shakibay Senobari Nader**

540 University of California Riverside,

541 Riverside, CA 92521-0144 (United States)

542 nshak006@ucr.edu

543

544

545 **Tables**

546

547 Table 1 – Velocity model used to generate synthetic seismograms.

Layer depth (km)	Vp (km/s)	Vp/Vs
0.00	4.10	1.84
2.00	5.10	1.77
7.86	5.79	1.79
17.80	6.34	1.73
42.00	8.00	1.78

548

549

550

551 Table 2 - Two RE families (Id_RE #0, #1) (from Shakibay Senobari and Funning, 2019).

552 Associated values (latitude, longitude, date, time and magnitude) for each event are taken from

553 NCEDC (2014).

554

Id_RE	Id_NCEDC	Lat (deg)	Long (deg)	Date (yyyy-mm-dd)	Time (hh:mm:sec)	Mag
0	122842	-122.99767	38.88830	1988-08-25	21:48:30.40	1.87
	484038	-122.99550	38.88750	1996-11-08	07:52:19.60	2.15
	21442564	-122.99617	38.88733	2005-03-01	10:01:21.00	2.08
	72388871	-122.99117	38.88750	2015-01-30	06:48:41.18	2.04
1	128170	-122.76884	38.54000	1988-12-07	06:47:34.21	2.04
	21128020	-122.76817	38.54183	2000-10-02	00:12:38.37	1.91
	71439381	-122.77167	38.54550	2010-07-30	05:57:34.30	1.72

555

556

557

558

559

560

561 **List of Figure Captions**

562

563 Figure 1 – FINDRES flow-chart. In yellow, we show the blocks related to data preparation and RE
564 identification; in blue and grey the blocks related to the CC and Δ S-P processing procedures
565 respectively.

566

567 Figure 2 - FINDRES applied to synthetic seismograms for pair of earthquakes characterized by
568 inter-event distance (d) of about 10 m. We generate synthetic seismograms with an epicentral
569 distance of about 15 km and the azimuth of about 226° for earthquakes pairs with the same focal
570 mechanism (strike, dip, rake: 242° , 40° , 80°). The inset in a) shows a sketch (non in scale) of the
571 geometry used for the generation of synthetics with $d=10$ m and seismic source radii (a and b).
572 Example of CC evaluation showing a) trace #1 and b) trace #2, and c) and d) cross-spectrum
573 analysis for P and S waves time window, respectively. a) and b) CC value (0.99) is calculated for
574 the Z component, waveforms are bandpass filtered between 1-25 Hz, and amplitudes are
575 normalized. The dotted red lines represent the time windows used in the cross-spectrum for P and S
576 waves. We chose 0.1 second before and 1.2 seconds after the P pick and 0.1 seconds before and 1.4
577 after the estimated S arrival travel time. c) The delay times for P and d) S-waves are estimated using
578 the cross-spectrum plot versus frequency. Delay times are obtained by fitting the slope of the points
579 with coherence above 0.88. Finally, the difference between relative P and S delay times is used to
580 estimate Δ S-P.

581

582 Figure 3 – Similarity space domain for synthetic seismograms: cross-correlation values (CC) and
583 absolute Δ S-P using theoretical (crosses) and estimated (circle) values. Each symbol in the figure
584 corresponds to only one station and one different pair of events. We generate synthetic seismograms
585 with an epicentral distance of about 15 km and the azimuth of about 226° for earthquakes pairs with

586 the same focal mechanism (strike, dip, rake: 242°, 40°, 80°), characterized by four different inter-
587 event distances, d , considering seismic source overlapping ($d=5, 10$ and 50 m) and non-overlapping
588 case ($d=100$ m). Purple: $d = 5$ m; red: $d = 10$ m; blue: $d = 50$ m; green: $d = 100$ m. The grey box
589 highlights the similarity space domain estimated for the $M_w = 1.5$ earthquake pairs (see text for
590 details). In the figure, the seismic source overlap that characterized the similarity space domain is
591 expressed in terms of inter-event distance (d) and seismic source radii (a and b). Overlapping RE
592 events are characterized by $d/(a+b) < 0.5$, non-overlapping events by $d/(a+b) > 1$. Similarity space
593 domains for synthetic seismograms without noise (a) and with random noise and different SNR
594 levels are shown; b) SNR about 5; c) SNR about 3, d) SNR about 2.

595

596 Figure 4 – FINDRES applied to a real dataset (event Id #21128020 and #71439381 in Table 2);
597 NTYB seismic station. Example of CC evaluation showing the seismic waveform of a) #21128020,
598 and b) #71439381 events, c) and d) cross-spectrum analysis for P and S waves time window
599 respectively. a) and b): the CC value (0.99) is calculated for the Z component, waveforms are
600 bandpass filtered between 1-20 Hz, amplitudes are normalized. The dotted red lines represent the
601 time windows used in the cross-spectrum for P and S waves. We choose 0.2 second before and 1.3
602 second after the P pick and 0.2 second before and 1.8 after the estimated S arrival travel time. The
603 delay times for c) P and d) S-waves is estimated using the cross-spectrum plot versus frequency.
604 Delay times are obtained fitting the slope of the points with coherence above 0.88. Finally, the
605 difference between relative P and S delay times is used to estimate $\Delta S-P$.

606

607 Figure 5 – FINDRES applied to a real dataset; a) similarity space domain obtained for a RE pair
608 (event Id #21128020 and #71439381 in Table 2). Each point in the graph corresponds to a seismic
609 station, colored according to the epicentral distance.

610

611 Figure 6 – FINDRES applied to a real dataset; HypoDD location obtained for a RE family (Id_RE
 612 #1 in Table 2), after the analysis of all the pair combinations. Red points show earthquake locations,
 613 the blue circles show the associated seismic source radii.

614

615

616 **Figures**

617

618 Figure 1 – FINDRES flow-chart. In yellow, we show the blocks related to data preparation and RE
 619 identification; in blue and grey the blocks related to the CC and $\Delta S-P$ processing procedures
 620 respectively.

621

622

623

624 Figure 2 - FINDRES applied to synthetic seismograms for pair of earthquakes characterized by
 625 inter-event distance (d) of about 10 m. We generate synthetic seismograms with an epicentral
 626 distance of about 15 km and the azimuth of about 226° for earthquakes pairs with the same focal
 627 mechanism (strike, dip, rake: 242° , 40° , 80°). The inset in a) shows a sketch (non in scale) of the
 628 geometry used for the generation of synthetics with $d=10$ m and seismic source radii (a and b).
 629 Example of CC evaluation showing a) trace #1 and b) trace #2, and c) and d) cross-spectrum
 630 analysis for P and S waves time window, respectively. a) and b) CC value (0.99) is calculated for
 631 the Z component, waveforms are bandpass filtered between 1-25 Hz, and amplitudes are
 632 normalized. The dotted red lines represent the time windows used in the cross-spectrum for P and S
 633 waves. We chose 0.1 second before and 1.2 seconds after the P pick and 0.1 seconds before and 1.4
 634 after the estimated S arrival travel time. c) The delay times for P and d) S-waves are estimated using
 635 the cross-spectrum plot versus frequency. Delay times are obtained by fitting the slope of the points

636 with coherence above 0.88. Finally, the difference between relative P and S delay times is used to
637 estimate $\Delta S-P$.

638

639

640

641 Figure 3 – Similarity space domain for synthetic seismograms: cross-correlation values (CC) and
642 absolute ΔS -P using theoretical (crosses) and estimated (circle) values. Each symbol in the figure
643 corresponds to only one station and one different pair of events. We generate synthetic seismograms
644 with an epicentral distance of about 15 km and the azimuth of about 226° for earthquakes pairs with
645 the same focal mechanism (strike, dip, rake: 242° , 40° , 80°), characterized by four different inter-
646 event distances, d , considering seismic source overlapping ($d=5$, 10 and 50 m) and non-overlapping
647 case ($d=100$ m). Purple: $d = 5$ m; red: $d = 10$ m; blue: $d = 50$ m; green: $d = 100$ m. The grey box
648 highlights the similarity space domain estimated for the $M_w = 1.5$ earthquake pairs (see text for
649 details). In the figure, the seismic source overlap that characterized the similarity space domain is
650 expressed in terms of inter-event distance (d) and seismic source radii (a and b). Overlapping RE
651 events are characterized by $d/(a+b) < 0.5$, non-overlapping events by $d/(a+b) > 1$. Similarity space
652 domains for synthetic seismograms without noise (a) and with random noise and different SNR
653 levels are shown; b) SNR about 5; c) SNR about 3, d) SNR about 2.

654
655
656
657
658
659
660

661

662

663

664 Figure 4 – FINDRES applied to a real dataset (event Id #21128020 and #71439381 in Table 2);
 665 NTYB seismic station. Example of CC evaluation showing the seismic waveform of a) #21128020,
 666 and b) #71439381 events, c) and d) cross-spectrum analysis for P and S waves time window
 667 respectively. a) and b): the CC value (0.99) is calculated for the Z component, waveforms are
 668 bandpass filtered between 1-20 Hz, amplitudes are normalized. The dotted red lines represent the
 669 time windows used in the cross-spectrum for P and S waves. We choose 0.2 second before and 1.3
 670 second after the P pick and 0.2 second before and 1.8 after the estimated S arrival travel time. The
 671 delay times for c) P and d) S-waves is estimated using the cross-spectrum plot versus frequency.
 672 Delay times are obtained fitting the slope of the points with coherence above 0.88. Finally, the
 673 difference between relative P and S delay times is used to estimate $\Delta S-P$.

674

676

677 Figure 5 – FINDRES applied to a real dataset; a) similarity space domain obtained for a RE pair
 678 (event Id #21128020 and #71439381 in Table 2). Each point in the graph corresponds to a seismic
 679 station, colored according to the epicentral distance.

680

681

682 Figure 6 – FINDRES applied to a real dataset; HypoDD location obtained for a RE family (Id_RE
 683 #1 in Table 2), after the analysis of all the pair combinations. Red points show earthquake locations,
 684 the blue circles show the associated seismic source radii.